

THE ATTITUDES AND BEHAVIORS OF COLLEGE STUDENTS TOWARDS LGBT INDIVIDUALS IN FPT UNIVERSITY DANANG AMONG DIFFERENT MAJORS

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Abstract

The prevalence of discrimination and oppression against LGBT community remains a significant concern within society, including college campuses. In order to address this issue, the present study aimed to investigate the attitudes toward LGBT individuals. A survey was conducted among 50 FPT university students representing five different majors on campus. The central hypothesis posited that males would generally exhibit a more heterosexist attitude towards the LGBT community. The results of the study supported this hypothesis, revealing that majors with a higher male population displayed greater levels of heterosexism compared to other majors. These findings hold the potential to contribute to a deeper understanding of societal attitudes and knowledge, ultimately fostering efforts to mitigate discrimination based on sexual orientation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the recognition and acceptance of diverse sexual orientations and gender identities have become increasingly important in the pursuit of equality and social justice worldwide. The LGBT (lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender) community has been at the forefront of this movement, advocating for equal rights and challenging societal norms (Johnson and Greeley, 2023). While progress has been made in some parts of the world, attitudes toward the LGBT community still vary greatly across different cultures and communities (Johnson and Greeley, 2023).

Vietnam, like many other countries, has seen growing awareness and discussion surrounding LGBT-related issues (Tuan, 2020). However, limited research has focused specifically on the attitudes and behaviors of FPT University Da Nang, one of the country's vibrant academic cities, towards individuals belonging to the LGBT community. Understanding the perspectives and behaviors of this crucial demographic is crucial for promoting inclusivity and fostering a supportive environment within educational institutions (Tuan, 2020).

The fact that in spite of the progress made by society in accepting diversity, many young individuals still harbor uneasy and bewildered perspectives toward non-heterosexual lifestyles (Sharpe, 2002). These perspectives contribute to the discrimination and oppression faced by the lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) community. According to Burn (2000), a study revealed that 77% of gay and lesbian college students experienced verbal insults based on their sexual orientation. Additionally, 27% encountered threats of physical violence, and 22% reported instances of being pursued or followed. Almost all the college students in this study acknowledged the presence of derogatory remarks on campus targeted at LGBT individuals.

When conducting research on attitudes toward homosexuality, it is crucial to acknowledge the limited availability of studies in this area. This scarcity might be attributed to the fact that homosexuality is a relatively recent and ongoing topic of interest in today's society. Although most of the studies discovered utilize the term "homosexuality," we will employ "homosexuality" and "LGBT" interchangeably. The majority of the available studies appear to be correlational in nature, as they compare diverse populations and their attitudes towards homosexuality. Similarly, this study aims to establish a connection between college students' attitudes toward homosexual individuals and their chosen academic majors. This means we will conduct a survey to assess the attitudes of undergraduate students from 5 different majors at FPT University. The reviewed articles provided insights into how individuals perceive someone as homosexual based on their characteristics.

1. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What are the male and female college students' attitudes and behaviors toward LGBT individuals compared across the curriculum in the following majors at FPT University Da Nang campus: Tourism and Hotel Management; Information Technology; Business Administration; Language; Design Graphic?
- What level of awareness do students on campus typically demonstrate regarding the term LGBT?
- What actionable suggestions can be provided to enhance the present negative circumstances side?

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To determine the attitudes of college students towards LGBT individuals by analyzing the responses to the key component statements on the survey.
- To investigate the familiarity with the term LGBT among college students by comparing the responses of those who are familiar with the term to those who are not.
- To analyze the understanding and knowledge about the LGBT community that students in Danang have and provide recommendations to help LGBT people deal with negative influences from others.

II. THEORETICAL BASIC AND RESEARCH MODEL

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

While a limited study indicated a connection between education majors exhibiting lower levels of heterosexism towards LGBT individuals compared to business majors, our study aims to expand upon this finding by incorporating a broader range of academic disciplines. We seek to investigate the relationship between chosen majors and heterosexist attitudes toward the LGBT community.

1.1. The definition of the LGBT community

Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender are collectively known as LGBT (Matharu *et al.*, 2012). A woman who is drawn to women is referred to as a Lesbian. A man who is drawn to other men is referred to as Gay. A person who finds attraction to both people of the same and opposite sex as them is called Bisexual. A person is born with a biological body as a male. Still, their physiology always instinctively urges them to become female and vice versa, the biological body is female but

the psychophysiology is male. Therefore, they decided to change their body to identify with the psychophysiology; they use hormones or transgender surgery to change their bodies. They are considered transgender (transgender from female to male) or transgendered (transgender from male to female) . Homosexuality is a natural sexual orientation and a sign of gender diversity in humans, according to scientists from numerous renowned institutions (Kinney, 2015). LGBT is not a disease or illness, society must appreciate the many manifestations of each person while upholding their rights (Ruse, 1981). But not everyone is aware of that truth. There are still several prejudices and stereotypes regarding this population in many places (Chatterjee, 2014). There is a misguided and constrained conception of gay desires.

LGBT people in some ways always strive to conceal their genuine proclivities. They are surrounded by gossip and terrified of being alone and being violent. They are classified as being in crisis and disarray (Banerjee *et al.*, 2018). Many transgender people tend to conceal their identity because they risk being verbally abused (Lyu, Shen, and Hesketh, 2020). Traditional norms and values can contribute to discrimination toward LGBT individuals.

Vietnam is an Asian country, partly influenced by Eastern culture. Therefore, Vietnam does not recognize marriage between persons of the same sex according to Article 8 of the 2014 Law on Marriage and Family and does not have any laws where LGBT people are protected (*Law on marriage and family*, 2014). Therefore, they do not have the sure protection of society, which leads to discrimination, wrong behaviors, and attitudes from people who are ignorant and prejudiced against the LGBT community. Because the LGBT community has not been recognized as cultural diversity in Vietnam (Tri, 2022). Cultural experts say that LGBT is a sensitive issue that has not been studied in a scientific and in-depth manner (Tri, 2022). Universities in Ho Chi Minh City and Dong Thap University have had studies on students' attitudes and behaviors toward homosexuals, but in Da Nang, there has not been a clear study on this (Tran Kim, 2018; Tuan, 2020). A part of students has a positive view of the LGBT community, but another part is still negative and has a vague and confused understanding of this community.

1.2. Investigate the common pressure of LGBT individual carrying.

- The attitude of the press

In general, the attitude of the press to the love of homosexuals tends to be more and more positive. However, the rate of stigma, looking at the negative side, is still quite high. When talking about celebrities, homosexuality is used as a detail to attract the reader's attention, showing the

wrong way of looking at the issue. This makes society have a negative view of homosexuality. Leads to negative attitudes and negative societal views may include adverse parental reactions to a child's gender nonconformity (Katz-Wise, Rosario and Tsappis, 2016).

- People's Attitude:

In general, in Vietnam, society's attitude towards homosexuality is either discriminatory at different levels or does not show obvious attitudes such as ignoring or not caring. A very small percentage of relatives have an open attitude toward homosexuals. Many people believe that homosexuality is influenced by Western lifestyles. However, this is not true. Moreover, most Southeast Asian countries have a strong prejudice against homosexuals except Thailand, which has not been colonized by the West in the past. Many people consider homosexuality to be abnormal or even morbid, especially in rural areas. According to an interview with a research article, someone said that they would not work with a civil society organization if it had an LGBT [lesbian, gay, bisexual, or transgender person] (Logie *et al.*, 2018). Most people do not know much about homosexuality. Many people do not distinguish between the concepts of homosexual, transsexual, and bisexual even though these are different concepts. Furthermore, the majority consider feminine men or masculine women to be homosexuals. However, a small number of people are beginning to recognize homosexuality and assert that homosexuality is not a disease. Attitudes towards homosexuals tend to be more open. In addition, the notion that more and more gay people are demanding today is also quite common. Therefore, the lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) community has to endure many negative experiences. more extreme on social inequality than the general public (Hughes, Damin and Heiden Rootes, 2017). This inequality is often reflected in occupational discrimination, health care disparities, labor rights, and gender issues (An and Batra, 2022).

- The attitude of relatives:

Parents may experience a number of different responses when faced with a disclosure of sexual minority orientation from their child, ranging from accepting to rejecting (Katz-Wise, Rosario, and Tsappis, 2016). Many parents feel hurt, surprised, angry, embarrassed, and bewildered when they learn that their child is gay. Behaving emotionally, they threatened, cursed, beat, and cut off finances, leaving their children without support. be held. Sadly, many parents have an attitude of denial about the truth about their child's gender. It is this attitude that has led some homosexuals to

hide themselves and then cause many unpredictable negative consequences. Very few people understand and accept the true gender of their children.

1.3. Investigate the common behaviors toward the LGBT community.

In the world today, the way to deal with people of the LGBT community in different countries is different. In some countries, anti-lesbian and gay behavior is still quite common. Attitudinal studies on anti-lesbian and gay behavior are intended to understand such attitudes and their interrelationships that can inform efforts to reduce their manifestation of anti-gay and lesbian behavior (Goodman and Moradi, 2008). However, despite evidence of the prevalence and potential negative consequences of anti-lesbian and gay behaviors, such as poor mental health and life satisfaction, and despite calls for greater understanding of anti-gay and lesbian behavior (Goodman and Moradi, 2008).

Some research suggests that hate crimes and anti-lesbian and gay behavior are influenced by complex situational factors (e.g., peer motivation, thrill-seeking motives), but anti-gay and lesbian attitudes are also associated with anti-lesbian and gay behavior (Goodman and Moradi, 2008). In addition to the proven associations between anti-lesbian and gay behavior and attitudes, several key correlations of anti-gay and lesbian attitudes are also associated with anti-gay behaviors in female and gay men. Someone has found that for college students, authoritarianism is associated with advocating for increased budget cuts for gay and lesbian student organizations (Goodman and Moradi, 2008). Thereby, it can be seen that there is a direct relationship between anti-gay and lesbian attitudes and behaviors, and these correlations can be a useful additional target in interventions to reduce behaviors against lesbians and gay men (Goodman and Moradi, 2008).

In Europe, an article on challenges to equality for LGBT people states: Lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender people commonly face obstacles in their daily lives: at the doctor's, at school, or simply walking hand-in-hand on the streets (Tuan, 2020). They are often bullied in classrooms or publicly attacked for simply being gay, lesbian, trans, or bisexual. Frequently they do not report incidents of hate crime or discrimination, partly out of a lack of trust in the respective authorities (Tuan, 2020). Some studies suggest that: lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) adolescents are vulnerable to poor health and social outcomes because of marginalization, stigma, and normative pressure against sexual and gender minorities. They face personal and interpersonal challenges associated with the coming-out process, whereby many milestones are experienced as difficult (Tuan, 2020).

In Vietnam, according to a research paper on the perception, attitude, and behavior of communicating with the LGBT community, negative behaviors in communication with the LGBT community of students are shown at a very low level. The majority of students also said that they “do not mention their gender issues” and “create conditions for the LGBT community to express themselves” (Tuan, 2020). They also conducted an interview and got back the results that very few people have negative thoughts and behaviors towards the LGBT community such as: "Avoid talking to people in the LGBT community, if they are present then I will find a way to withdraw or stop being quiet and not talk to them." Most of the students showed positive behaviors, such as showing joy in receiving, enthusiastically exchanging and listening to each other's ideas, etc (Tuan, 2020).

1.4. Literature gap

According to Müller-Bloch and Kranz, 2015 and Robinson, Saldanha, and Mckoy, 2011, there are seven distinct research gap types, namely the evidence gap, knowledge gap, practical-knowledge gap, methodology gap, empirical gap, theoretical gap, and population gap. In the study investigating the attitudes and behaviors of college students in Da Nang, especially at FPT University, towards the LGBT community, the researchers have identified various gaps in the existing literature. These gaps can be categorized into two types of research gaps, specifically the knowledge gap and the population gap.

a. Knowledge gap

The knowledge gap pertains to the lack of information or comprehension within the existing body of literature and theories from relevant research domains. It can also occur when the study's findings do not align with the anticipated outcomes (Müller-Bloch and Kranz, 2015). Previous research papers mostly focus on college students' attitudes toward individuals belonging to the LGBT community among students in their areas. It is noticed that these studies only identify the attitudes toward the LGBT community in higher education (Schott-Ceccacci and Holland, 2009) or explore college students' acceptance and attitudes toward the LGBT community (Kamarudin *et al.*, 2021). However, there is still a lack of research papers specifically focusing on both the attitudes and behaviors of college students toward individuals within the LGBT community, especially at FPT University in Danang City.

b. Population gap

The population gap signifies inadequate research or underrepresentation of particular groups in the current literature, such as age, gender, race, or ethnicity (Robinson, Saldanha, and Mckoy, 2011). It is evident that previous research papers examining the attitudes and behaviors of college students toward the LGBT community have primarily concentrated on specific geographic regions or countries. May be mentioned as there is a research paper about the attitudes toward homosexuals among students at a Canadian University (Schellenberg, Hirt, and Sears, 1999). The two other research papers are also in Vietnam, the first one is about the perceptions and attitudes of college students at Dong Thap University toward LGBT individuals (Tran Kim, 2018), and the rest one is about awareness, attitudes, and behaviors in communication with the LGBT community of students in Ho Chi Minh City (Tuan, 2020). Nevertheless, the authors intend to adopt a unique strategy by conducting a case study specifically targeting college students in Da Nang, Vietnam. Their objective is to gain a more profound understanding of the attitudes and behaviors of college students at FPT University in Da Nang towards the LGBT community, with this case study serving as a focal point. This methodology enables the collection of detailed data to explore the perspectives of college students and their attitudes and behaviors toward people belonging to the LGBT community.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Learn about The Feminist Theory Model

Feminist theory is a branch of critical theory, which in general has the purpose of destabilizing systems of power and oppression. The purpose of using a feminist lens is that in order to enable the discovery of how people interact within systems and possibly offer solutions to confront and eradicate oppressive systems and structures. Feminist theory considers the lived experience of any person/people, not only just for women, with an emphasis on oppression. The truth is there may not be a consensus on where feminist theory fits as a theory or paradigm, disruption of oppression is a core tenet of feminist work. (Egbert and Roe, 2020). As Hooks (2000) states, “Simply put, feminism theory is a movement to end sexism, sexist exploitation and oppression. I liked this definition because it does not imply that men were the enemy”.

Feminist research has helped us better understand how the division of labor between genders is complex and constantly evolving. It believes in political, economic, and social equality for men and women and does not focus on differences or similarities between them, nor does it seek to exclude men or solely promote women's issues. Feminist theory aims to bring about positive change and knowledge by recognizing and challenging power dynamics and forms of oppression. Feminist

theory proposes that when power and oppression are acknowledged and disrupted, understanding, advocacy, and change can be found.

Figure 1
Model of Feminist Theory

2.2. APPLYING THE FEMINIST THEORY TO THE RESEARCH.

The study employs the Feminist Theory (Strong, Cohen and DeVault, 2005), which explores how gender and gender roles shape families. Traditionally, men were expected to display masculine traits while women were expected to exhibit femininity. This theory suggests that both genders are constrained by specific roles. Furthermore, it extends to other oppressed groups defined by age, class, ethnicity, race, disability, or sexual orientation. In the context of this study, the Feminist Theory predicts that our findings will align with societal assumptions regarding males and females. It suggests that our sample's attitudes and behaviors will reflect heterosexual and traditional gender roles, with men predominantly establishing these norms. Consequently, it is likely that men will have stronger adherence to gender role boundaries. Additionally, since gender roles were socially constructed by men, it is anticipated that males will demonstrate a more heterosexist attitude.

2.3. GENERATE HYPOTHESES BASED ON THE FEMINIST THEORY FRAMEWORK.

a) HYPOTHESIS ABOUT ATTITUDES.

Feminist Theory suggests that gender roles are socially constructed by men, attributing specific roles to both males and females. Historical factors have led to men feeling a stronger

obligation to adhere to these gender role boundaries. The theory predicts that men are likely to hold more heterosexist attitudes.

H1: Male-dominated majors will exhibit more heterosexist attitudes compared to the others.

b) HYPOTHESIS ABOUT BEHAVIORS.

Social Cognitive Theory proposes that behaviors are influenced by a combination of personal factors, environmental factors, and cognitive processes. In the context of gender roles, individuals' behaviors are shaped by their beliefs, observations of others, and the consequences associated with those behaviors. The theory predicts that individuals in male-dominated majors may demonstrate behaviors that reinforce traditional gender norms.

H2: Male-dominated majors may exhibit behaviors that reinforce traditional gender norms.

c) HYPOTHESIS ABOUT KNOWLEDGE AWARENESS AFFECTING ATTITUDES AND BEHAVIORS.

Feminist theory challenges societal norms and inequalities related to gender. When it comes to the hypothesis that those who are familiar with the term "LGBT" have more positive attitudes toward LGBT individuals, applying feminist theory highlights how this familiarity aligns with feminist values of questioning traditional gender roles. By familiarizing oneself with the term "LGBT," individuals may demonstrate a level of awareness and knowledge regarding diverse sexual orientations and gender identities. This awareness aligns with feminist values, as it signifies a conscious effort to challenge traditional gender roles and norms. Moreover, being familiar with the term "LGBT" may indicate exposure to inclusive ideas and concepts, leading to a questioning of heteronormative and cisnormative assumptions.

H3: People with higher knowledge about LGBT terms will demonstrate more positive attitudes and engage in more supportive behaviors towards the LGBT community.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN, METHOD, AND TOOLS

1. RESEARCH METHOD

Participants

This study took place at FPT University Danang. Participants included 50 students at FPT University Da Nang Campus, in which the survey took place in 5 major groups: Business administration; Language; Design and communication major; Information technology; Hospitality and tourism management, each specialized group will have 10 people to participate in the survey. Of these fifty, 25 of the participants were male and 25 were female. There were 20 participants between the ages of 18-21, 20 between the ages of 22-25, and the remaining 10 participants were 25 years or older.

Research Design

The purpose of this study was to understand the current attitudes and behaviors of the sample group that participated in the survey, and based on those data to broaden the horizons of a larger group of students on campus. The study used a nonprobability sampling design pattern to easily collect information from students in specific majors. The students who participated in the survey were mainly those who were likely to have the necessary information and were willing to share it. Finally, data were collected using a self-administered survey which included prepared questions, as this is the most effective method due to the fast pace of our research course, overall convenience, low cost of using the survey, and data collection directly on campus and can collect data quickly.

Data Collection Instrument

To address students' attitudes and behaviors toward LGBT individuals, we created a survey. The survey contains information regarding basic definitions of gender in the LGBT community. The survey included three demographic questions related to major, age, and educational status. The participants were then given a number of closed statements, which are the dependent variables, and then the participants were asked to circle the answer that best describes their attitude based on the scale measure Likert 5 points from one (strongly disagree) to five (strongly agree). The questions build on our understanding of the literature and its implications for attitudes and behaviors toward LGBT individuals. The questions included 2 main parts that have different components so we could analysis later using the Feminist model.

Procedure

To collect data for this study, we approached a number of students on campus between 8-11 July 2023. When approached, the students were given a form about their perception. We conducted

a survey in FPT University of Danang with subjects related to the studied majors. To maintain the highest possible security and in the hope of making the survey more accurate, the participants will be scanned with a code on their phone that we have created and it will lead the students to the link of the survey. To ensure sample size, we have distributed and set a target on the number of surveys for team members to avoid missing data.

Data Analysis Plan

To improve the validity of data, the system will force survey participants to fill out all information on the survey before they can submit and complete the survey. The first questions in the survey aimed to describe the characteristics of the participants such as age, academic status, and major. In these three questions, the only independent variable was major (MAJOR). Each attitudes, and behaviors statement is also given a number of abbreviations.

2.EXPECTED RESULTS

Firstly, the results of this study determine the attitudes and behaviors of the FPT Da Nang student community, thereby suggesting results, providing detailed information and how individuals perceive someone are homosexuals based on their characteristics. Likewise, this study aimed to establish a link between university students' attitudes towards homosexuals and their chosen major of study. To make the right judgments and have a more specific view of the LGBT community.

Second, the research results can explore the degree of attitude and behavior of FPT Da Nang students towards the LGBT community, which means that we will conduct a survey to assess the attitudes of FPT student's university students from 5 different majors at FPT University, thereby helping to take measures to protect the LGBT community. In addition, the study also provides a theoretical basis for further studies on the LGBT community. The study results also provide a deeper understanding of the definitions of terms that describe a person's sexual orientation, namely when they have sexual orientation with people of the same or different genders. This will contribute to raising awareness, attitudes and behaviors in social life, spiritual balance and satisfaction with the LGBT community. After that, students and everyone will have a better view of the LGBT community. In addition, attitudes and behaviors towards the LGBT community will be more standard and open in the future.

Hopefully our team will complete the article completely and accurately to have the opportunity to make the report more known in the future. To bring useful information to everyone. And also make a useful contribution to the scientific research of mankind. With the advantage of easy access to research subjects, the current research only focuses on the student community at FPT University Da Nang, so the results are still limited sample size limitations. Besides, the research results can only be generalized as a research basis for other fields, and the basis for accessing and evaluating other research fields. Proposing for future research directions, other researchers can expand the scope of the study to provide a more comprehensive argument base.

3. RESEARCH RESULT

Using cross-tabulation analysis, we can compare the results between specific majors (MAJOR) that are independent variables, with dependent variables. After consulting with many people, we found that ten variables (familiar, know, comfort, social, content, equal, self-learning, support, express, discriminate) are reliable enough to measure our concept (The attitudes and behaviors of college students towards LGBT individuals in FPT University Danang among different majors). And this survey is also a reliable measure of our central concept and is inspired by The Feminist theory and literature review. The below variables are enough to give us the necessary information about the students' attitudes and behaviors toward individuals in the LGBT community.

3.1. ATTITUDE SURVEY VARIABLES

FAMILIAR						
Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business administration	0%	0%	10%	30%	60%	100%
Graphic Design	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	100%
Hospitality and tourism	0%	10%	10%	40%	40%	100%
Information technology	10%	10%	10%	40%	30%	100%
Language	10%	0%	10%	30%	50%	100%

KNOW						
Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business administration	0%	10%	10%	30%	50%	100%
Graphic Design	0%	0%	20%	30%	50%	100%
Hospitality and tourism	10%	0%	10%	50%	30%	100%
Information technology	10%	0%	10%	60%	20%	100%
Language	0%	10%	10%	40%	40%	100%

COMFORT						
Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business administration	0%	10%	10%	30%	50%	100%

Graphic Design	0%	20%	20%	30%	30%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	0%	10%	10%	40%	40%	100%
Information Technology	10%	10%	20%	30%	30%	100%
Language	0%	0%	10%	40%	50%	100%

SOCIAL

Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business Administration	10	10	20	20	40	100%
Graphic Design	0%	0%	20%	40%	40%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	0%	20%	20%	30%	30%	100%
Information Technology	30%	10%	20%	10%	30%	100%
Language	0%	20%	40%	20%	20%	100%

CONTENT

Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business Administration	0%	0%	30%	20%	50%	100%
Graphic Design	0%	10%	50%	30%	10%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	10%	10%	30%	50%	0%	100%
Information Technology	40%	30%	30%	0%	0%	100%
Language	20%	10%	30%	30%	10%	100%

EQUAL

Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business Administration	0%	0%	20%	20%	60%	100%
Graphic Design	10%	10%	20%	30%	30%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	10%	0%	10%	40%	40%	100%
Information Technology	10%	10%	30%	40%	10%	100%
Language	0%	10%	0%	40%	50%	100%

Note. (MAJOR)= Business administration; Language; Graphic Design; Information technology; Hospitality and tourism management; (FAMILIAR)=Familiarity with the term LGBT; (KNOW)= Knowing an LGBT individual; (COMFORT)= Being comfortable in the presence of an LGBT individual; (SOCIAL)= Spending social time with LGBT individuals; (CONTENT)= Importance of having LGBT content in all courses; (EQUAL)= LGBT individuals should have all the same rights as heterosexuals in VN.

3.2. BEHAVIOR SURVEY VARIABLES

SELF-LEARNING

Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business Administration	0%	0%	40%	50%	10%	100%
Graphic Design	10%	0%	10%	20%	60%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	0%	0%	20%	40%	40%	100%
Information Technology	20%	30%	40%	10%	0%	100%
Language	0%	0%	30%	40%	30%	100%

DISCRIMINATE

Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business Administration	20%	10%	60%	10%	0%	100%

Graphic Design	10%	70%	20%	0%	0%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	20%	20%	50%	10%	0%	100%
Information Technology	0%	10%	20%	50%	20%	100%
Language	20%	50%	30%	0%	0%	100%

SUPPORT

Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business Administration	0%	0%	40%	30%	30%	100%
Graphic Design	0%	0%	20%	20%	60%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	0%	0%	20%	40%	40%	100%
Information Technology	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%	100%
Language	0%	10%	60%	20%	10%	100%

EXPRESS

Category	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Business Administration	0%	0%	10%	60%	30%	100%
Graphic Design	0%	0%	20%	50%	30%	100%
Hospitality and Tourism	0%	0%	10%	80%	10%	100%
Information Technology	10%	50%	20%	10%	10%	100%
Language	0%	0%	70%	10%	20%	100%

Note. (MAJOR)= Business administration; Graphic Design; Hospitality and tourism management; Information technology; Language; (SELF-LEARNING)= Find and learn about the LGBT community by oneself.; (DISCRIMINATE)= Discriminate against LGBT; (SUPPORT)= Help and support people of the LGBT community; (EXPRESS)= Express opinions and protect the rights of the LGBT community in discussions.

4. RESEARCH DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

4.1. ATTITUDE SURVEY ANALYSIS

In general, current statistical data shows that the gender ratio in various surveying fields is approximately equal, except for the IT sector, where the male ratio is higher, accounting for 80% of the gender ratio in major. The survey showed that the level of familiarity with the term LGBT (FAMILIAR) of industry groups is quite high and the level of knowledge (KNOW) of industry groups is also high. However, regarding the content variable (CONTENT), none of the Information technology students felt that LGBT content in their courses was necessary. This could be interpreted as a matter of gender or whether they feel LGBT content is relevant to an Information technology course. Furthermore, Information Technology participants had a low level of comfort (COMFORT) compared to other industries.

It is suggested that positive attitudes toward LGBT people and understanding of these individuals are closely linked (Kim *et al.*, 1998). This idea is supported in our study as it found that virtually all majors have a high degree of comfort (COMFORT) with LGBT individuals. This is

closely related to the amount of social contact time (SOCIAL) with LGBT individuals. Mainly, people who spend less time socializing and interacting with LGBT people will have lower comfort levels than those who regularly socialize with individuals of the LGBT community.

People who often work and come into direct contact with people will be more receptive and understanding of the diversity of the community (Kim *et al.*, 1998). Since the Business administration major focuses on working with many other individuals in contact with many different people, their comfort level (COMFORT) and equality are quite high. However, when analyzing the results, it was found that while the Business administration major had a high level of comfort (COMFORT) and equality (EQUAL), the majors in Language and Hospitality and tourism management had even higher levels higher altitude. And the two majors Information Technology and Graphic Design major are mainly working on computers, so the level of social contact (SOCIAL) is lower, which also means the level of comfort (COMFORT) and equality (EQUAL) is lower than in other industries.

We question whether more positive beliefs and attitudes towards LGBT individuals are related to knowing a lesbian or gay person. However, 90% of participants in the Information technology industry claimed to know a person who was homosexual (KNOW), however, their responses to the rest of the variables indicated that they had the most negative attitudes of all the variables industry group in our study. This raises the question of whether someone's level of knowledge about an LGBT person affects how you feel about them.

4.2. BEHAVIOR SURVEY ANALYSIS

Overall, the results supported the hypothesis that majors with higher percentages of men, in which man roles are highly considered, have less positive views of LGBT individuals. Statistics show that Information Technology majors have more “Disagree” or “ Strongly Disagree” answers than other majors. According to Herek (1988), the average heterosexual male exhibits more anti-gay hostility than the average heterosexual female (Herek, 1988). Typically, this is evidenced when 20% of respondents have agreed with unequal behavior towards LGBT individuals (DISCRIMINATE) and up to 40% of participants “strongly disagree” to support LGBT individuals in the variable (SUPPORT). Regarding the self-learning variable (SELF-LEARNING), no participants did their own research on LGBT-related information because they had no regrets about it.

In order to receive comprehensive support and support, it is necessary to have an understanding and information capital for LGBT individuals that is large enough, not only through external contact. This is also affected by the expectation (EXPRESS) to learn about the policy for the LGBT community. In addition, IT students have very little social contact and work with the LGBT community, so the level of interest and expectation (EXPRESS) of this industry is also lower than other industries such as BA, GD, HT, and Lang.

As we mentioned above, people in majors that work directly with people are generally more receptive and understanding of human diversity (Kim et al., 1998). As a result, we found that the Business Administration and Hospitality & Tourism majors tend to be willing to support LGBT individuals higher than the rest. However, when analyzing the results, it was surprising that while Business Administration and Hospitality & Tourism majors had high levels of support (SUPPORT), Graphic Design majors had even higher levels. Besides that, Language majors keep a neutral stance with the U rate being over half (60%).

With the term express opinions and protect the rights (EXPRESS) of LGBT individuals, similar to support (SUPPORT), the three majors that had the positive rate are Business Administration, Hospitality & Tourism, and Graphic Design. Also, it's unexpectedly surprising that the Language major group still chooses not to take any side, and the IT major has the most negative indicator.

As previously mentioned, the theory of Feminist Theory (Strong, Cohen and DeVault, 2005) posits that men play a significant role in shaping societal gender norms. This theory suggests that both males and females are expected to adhere to distinct gender roles. Due to various historical influences, men tend to have a stronger inclination to abide by these gender role expectations. Based on this theory, it was anticipated that men would display more heterosexist attitudes. The findings of the study supported this hypothesis.

4.3. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

One of the key limitations of this research revolves around the sample size employed. The study's small sample size prevents us from making broad generalizations about the wider population. Furthermore, the use of a non-random sampling approach further restricts the generalizability of our findings, limiting them specifically to college students within the selected majors.

Another potential limitation worth noting is the sensitive nature of the topic under investigation, which might have influenced participants to respond in a socially desirable manner rather than expressing their true attitudes and behaviors. Expanding on this point, the sensitivity surrounding the topic could have introduced response bias and affected the accuracy of the collected data. Therefore, cautious interpretation is necessary when considering the outcomes of this study. Future research with larger and more diverse samples, employing random sampling techniques, could enhance the generalizability and validity of findings concerning attitudes and behaviors towards the LGBT community at our university.

4.4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this research have important implications for practitioners and future research. It is crucial for family practitioners to acknowledge their biases and ensure they do not hinder their work. This study highlights the need for more education on LGBT issues practitioners and educators can benefit from professional development workshops, conferences, and on-the-job training to enhance their understanding of LGBT issues. By equipping educators with better knowledge, they can effectively teach and provide the necessary information for fostering acceptance among students, as acceptance is learned at an early age.

For future research, it is recommended to conduct studies with individuals who have never attended a college to determine the role of education in shaping attitudes, and behaviors as well as to explore the influence of gender roles. Such research would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing attitudes toward LGBT individuals.

In conclusion, this study has shed light on attitudes toward LGBT people, emphasizing the importance of education and knowledge dissemination to combat discrimination based on sexual orientation. It is crucial to eliminate the social stigma associated with homosexuality, and education is identified as a key strategy for achieving this goal. Recognizing the significance of gender in education and societal change is essential when striving to create a more inclusive and accepting society.

5. THESIS STRUCTURE

1. Introduction

The introduction to our research paper aims to provide an overview of the research topic on attitudes and behaviors of college students towards LGBT individuals in FPT University Danang

among different majors. The introduction includes Background, Research questions, Research objective, Scope and Limitations. It succinctly summarizes the main points and findings of the paper.

2. Literature Review

In a research paper, a literature review thoroughly examines previous research and scholarly articles that pertain to a particular research subject. It provides an extensive overview of the existing body of knowledge in the field, encompassing theoretical and empirical studies, research techniques, results, and final assessments. We read articles from various sources, both positive and negative, to gain a better understanding of the different aspects of the topic. By identifying the differences and gaps in previous studies, we aim to find a breakthrough point for this report. Therefore, we will search for additional literature on this subject.

3. Methods

We chose the methods to help collect the data, how it was analyzed, and explained why we chose it. It fits the question and makes sure to also explain what the approaches are and how we've tried to minimize them. Discussing the shortcomings of your research gives you more credibility, as it shows the reader that you are aware of its limitations.

Regarding the research method, we discussed in Part 4 of this proposal.

4. Results

Results will be made when we have enough data from the survey and conduct data analysis. In this section, this study uses cross-tabulation analysis, can compare the results between specific majors (MAJOR) as independent variables, with dependent variables, combined with the opinion survey of many people, for comprehensive data collection. Quantitative surveys will provide statistical data. By using both methods, we aim to capture essential information about university students' attitudes towards the LGBT community in Danang.

5. Discussion and conclusion

After taking measures of data analysis, the method leads to the results of the study. We discussed including analysis and interpretation of the data collected, commented on the results, strengths and limitations of the study, and explained the significance of the study, compared and compared the results with many other studies. Help the research article to be accurate, giving people a better and more accurate view of the content we research in the future.

In conclusion, we summarize the main findings and major contributions of the research to

the community, re-emphasize the practical significance of the research and reinforce the importance and relevance of the contents to the goals research target.

REFERENCES

- An, D. and Batra, K. (2022) 'Trends in scientific output on the lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) community research: A bibliometric analysis of the literature', *Journal of Health and Social Sciences*, 7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.19204/2022/TRND8>.
- Banerjee, S.C. et al. (2018) 'Knowledge, Beliefs, and Communication Behavior of Oncology Health-care Providers (HCPs) regarding Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender (LGBT) Patient Health care', *Journal of Health Communication*, 23(4), pp. 329–339. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730.2018.1443527>.
- Chatterjee, S. (2014) 'Problems Faced by LGBT People in the Mainstream Society: Some Recommendations.', in. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Problems-Faced-by-LGBT-People-in-the-Mainstream-Chatterjee/952e3f6e459d42a798f4b6a43d3307b79bf280f1#cited-papers>.
- Egbert, J. and Roe, M. (2020) *Theoretical Models for Teaching and Research (CC:BY-NC 4.0 license)*.
- Goodman, M.B. and Moradi, B. (2008) 'Attitudes and behaviors toward lesbian and gay persons: Critical correlates and mediated relations.', *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 55(3), pp. 371–384. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.55.3.371>.
- Herek, G.M. (1988) 'Heterosexuals' Attitudes toward Lesbians and Gay Men: Correlates and Gender Differences', *The Journal of Sex Research*, 25(4), pp. 451–477.
- Hughes, R., Damin, C. and Heiden Rootes, K. (2017) 'Where's the LGBT in Integrated Care Research? A Systematic Review', *Families, Systems, & Health*, 35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/fsh0000290>.
- Johnson, T. and Greeley, A. (2023) 'College Students' Attitudes toward LGBT Individuals College Students' Attitudes toward LGBT Individuals'.
- Kamarudin, A. et al. (2021) 'Exploring college students' acceptance and attitude toward the LGBT community', *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24, p. 2020.
- Katz-Wise, S.L., Rosario, M. and Tsappis, M. (2016) 'LGBT Youth and Family Acceptance', *Pediatric clinics of North America*, 63(6), pp. 1011–1025. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcl.2016.07.005>.
- Kim, B.S.K. et al. (1998) 'A Multicultural Study of University Students' Knowledge of and Attitudes Toward Homosexuality', *The Journal of Humanistic Education and Development*, 36(3), pp. 171–182. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2164-4683.1998.tb00387.x>.
- Kinney, R.L. (2015) 'Homosexuality and scientific evidence: On suspect anecdotes, antiquated data, and broad generalizations', *The Linacre Quarterly*, 82(4), pp. 364–390. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1179/2050854915Y.0000000002>.
- Law on marriage and family* (2014) *Thư viện pháp luật*. Available at: <https://thuvienphapluat.vn/van-ban/EN/Quyen-dan-su/Law-No-52-2014-QH13-on-marriage-and-family/260341/tieng-anh.aspx>.
- Logie, C. et al. (2018) 'Experiences and perceptions of social constraints and social change among lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender persons in Lesotho', *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 21, pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691058.2018.1498539>.
- Lyu, J., Shen, X. and Hesketh, T. (2020) 'Sexual Knowledge, Attitudes and Behaviours among Undergraduate Students in China—Implications for Sex Education', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(18), p. 6716. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17186716>.
- Matharu, K. et al. (2012) 'Medical students' attitudes toward gay men', *BMC Medical Education*, 12(1), p. 71. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-12-71>.
- Müller-Bloch, C. and Kranz, J. (2015) 'A Framework for Rigorously Identifying Research Gaps

- in Qualitative Literature Reviews', in. *International Conference on Interaction Sciences*. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-Framework-for-Rigorously-Identifying-Research-in-M%C3%BCller-Bloch-Kranz/73596c4957deab7c7a3fd1d4261994e47be1508c> (Accessed: 19 June 2023).
- Robinson, K.A., Saldanha, I.J. and Mckoy, N.A. (2011) 'Development of a framework to identify research gaps from systematic reviews', *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 64(12), pp. 1325–1330. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2011.06.009>.
- Ruse, M. (1981) 'Are Homosexuals Sick?', in Ruse, M., *Is Science Sexist?* Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, pp. 245–272. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-8443-1_10.
- Schellenberg, E.G., Hirt, J. and Sears, A. (1999) 'Attitudes Toward Homosexuals Among Students at a Canadian University', *Sex Roles*, 40(1), pp. 139–152. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018838602905>.
- Schott-Ceccacci, M. and Holland, L. (2009) 'Attitudes toward the LGBT Community in Higher Education'.
- Strong, B., Cohen, T.F. and DeVault, C. (2005) *The marriage and family experience: intimate relationships in a changing society*. 9th ed. (Instructor's ed.). Belmont, CA: Thomson Wadsworth.
- Tran Kim N. (2018) 'Nhận thức, thái độ của sinh viên Trường Đại học Đồng Tháp về người đồng tính', *Dong Thap University Journal of Science*, (32), pp. 11–15. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.52714/dthu.32.6.2018.581>.
- Tuan, P.V. (2020) 'AWARENESS, ATTITUDES AND BEHAVIORS IN COMMUNICATION WITH THE LGBT COMMUNITY OF STUDENTS IN HO CHI MINH CITY, VIETNAM', *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt / Egyptology*, 17(4), pp. 328–338. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48080/jae.v17i4.292>.